

IMPACT OF GEOLOGICAL VARIABLES ON GYPSUM MINERALISATION: ASSESSMENT OF
THE GUYUK GYPSUM OCCURRENCES, N. E. NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Field observations are used to assess the impact of geomorphic, lithologic and physicochemical to ascertain their extent of control on gypsum formation and accumulation in Guyuk area. Varying quantities of gypsiferous beds are associated with mainly mudstone and highly fossiliferous – fissured limestone at depths between 0.02 to 9.12m and altitude 219.3 – 473.62m. Integration of the field evidences reveal that gypsum mineralisation is not restricted to a particular depth/altitude range rather its absence or copious occurrences depend on presence of limestone beds in the area. Inductively, dolomitization is given as the process of gypsum mineralisation in Guyuk area.

KEYWORDS: Gypsum mineralisation, Guyuk, Nigeria, controlling factors, dolomitization.

INTRODUCTION

Mineralisation is known to relate to specific geologic features, which exert some measure of control and determine the occurrence of mineral deposits in any environment. Some workers, including Uzuakpunwa, (1981); Offodile (1982); Sonnenfeld (1991) and Uma (1998) have examined exploratory framework for evaporites and emphasise the role of structure and stratigraphy in their formation, accumulation and distribution. The determining factors that influence the formation and localization of gypsum in an environment are seen as geological variables. They include geomorphic, lithologic and physicochemical variables. Assessing the impact of these geological variables using the field observations of gypsum occurrences can be valuable aids to prospecting and exploration. In this work, the contributory roles of geomorphology, lithology and physicochemical processes to gypsum formation and accumulation in sediments within Guyuk area are examined. Probable findings would help subsequent researchers in setting up prospecting strategies to discover gypsum deposits.

Location and Geology of the Study Area

Guyuk is located between Latitude 9^o45'N and 10^o00'N and Longitude 11^o46'E and 12^o00'E, in Northeastern Nigeria (Fig. 1). The area has been affected by wrench faults and E-W trending submeridian normal faults, and has lithologic attributes known to favour the formation of evaporites (Burke et al, 1970; Olade, 1975; Benkhelil, 1982, 1986; Braide, 1992; Zaborski et al, 1997; Uma, 1998).

Though these favourable mineralizing frameworks are satisfied in the Guyuk area, and preliminary exploratory investigations (GSG, 1989; Ntekim, 1999) reveal three main occurrences of gypsum in Dukul, Gunda and Lamza districts of the area; some of the stratigraphic units are sparsely mineralised e.g. Jessu Formation and, in mineralized units, the quantity, varieties and quality vary from one location to the other (Carter et al, 1963; Ntekim, 1999). This contribution is therefore an attempt to evaluate these variations using field observations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field study of the shale – carbonate lithologic units relevant to gypsum mineralisation around known or established deposits and their environs in Guyuk area was carried out involving establishing the location, altitude and depth of occurrence of gypsum-bearing litho-units using GPS equipment, and examining and characterizing the exposed carrier litho-beds. This was to ascertain the impact of the various variables on gypsum mineralisation in the study area. The rocks comprising shale, limestone and clay were studied in a

total of thirteen (13) locations, including Dukul, Gudenyi, Bobini, Lamza, Swenswithire, Walu, Lakoro, Sukuliye, Gwalura, Gunda, Gendaure, Gwana and Kola (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1 MAP OF PART OF GUYUK AREA SHOWING THE GEOLOGY AND MAJOR LIMESTONE AND GYPSUM DEPOSITS (modified from Ntekim, 1999; Ntekim & Zira, 2001)

Geomorphic variables

In the field, the gypsum minerals generally outcrop on hill slopes of stream channels within different stratigraphic units, associated with shale, limestone and mudstone. Examination of the exposed beds shows that the shale beds are mostly grey and brownish-yellow in colour, fissile and friable in most locations, but occur as loose sediments in Sukuliye. They are encountered mainly at an altitude of between 210.08m (in Lakoro) and 473.62m at Gudenyi and a depth range of from 0.02m (in Lakoro) to 9.12m in Walu (Fig.2 and Table 1). Thickness of the shale beds generally increases down the profile varying between 3m in Walu and 0.03m in Gendaure (Fig.2). Limestone beds are fossiliferous, except in few locations; grey in colour and thinly bedded and occur as surface debris or broken slabs in some locations. They are exposed mainly at an altitude of between 209.9m at Lakoro and 473.49m at Gudenyi (Table 2) and a depth range from 0.0 (in Sukuliye) to 13.55m (in Dukul). The limestone beds decrease in thickness down the section, varying between 0.6m in Dukul and 0.05m in Gendaure (Fig.2). The clay beds occur at an altitude of between 208.7m at Lakoro and 349.92m at Walu (Table 2). The beds range in thickness between 1.0m in Lakoro and 0.15m at Lamza; and a depth range from 0.1 to 4.05m. The gypsum minerals are whitish to gray in colour; the recovered forms are tabular or flaky sheet (selenite) types in most locations, granular (alabaster) types in sections of Walu, fibrous, cloudy or chalky coloured (satin spar) type in Swenswithire and Gudenyi, and rosette-like aggregates and curled elongated crystal types in Sukuliye. The gypsum beds are found to accumulate much within the depth ranges between 219.3 – 231.95m; 258.9 – 308.9m; 320.8 – 363.97m and 372.9 – 473.62m (Table1 & 2). Examination of the depth ranges reveal that gypsiferous host materials mainly occur within a depth profile of 0.02 – 9.12m (Fig.2).

Lithologic variables

Many workers (Orajaka, 1972; Matheis, 1979; 1987; Olade, 1980; Matheis et al, 1982) observe that mineralisation of the Nigerian mineral deposits is controlled by associated rock types, structures and sedimentary processes or their combined effects. Encountered stratigraphic sections reveal that the gypsum bodies are associated with shale – limestone – clay alternations in Gunda, Gendaure, Lamza, Walu, Dukul, Gudenyi, Sukuliye, Kola, and a location at Lakoro. Occurrences in Walu, Gwalura and Swenswithire are associated with barren shale – gypsiferous shale – mudstone alternations while that at Gwana is mainly sandstone – clay alternation [see Fig.2]. Comparatively, field evidence shows that the shale – mudstone alternations are more gypsiferous than others. Association of the carbonate rocks (calcareous sandstones and limestone) with the shale in Guyuk area depicts a carbonated environment, which is a necessary chemical condition for gypsum mineralisation (cf. Evans, 1978; Sonnenfeld, 1991; Uma, 1998). The gypsum occurrences in Dukul are hosted in Dukul Formation, those in Sukuliye, Gunda and Gwalura are in Sekule Formation, occurrences in Walu, Swenswithire and Lamza are in Numanha Formation, while those

in Lakoro and Gudenyi are in Jessu Formation (see Fig.1). As observed by Offodile (1982), the mineralising evaporitic fluids are mainly issued from the interbedded shale units within the transitional Yolde Formation while the shale rock units host the gypsiferous materials.

Physicochemical variables

Gypsum is formed as product of chemical weathering and is precipitated from aqueous solutions in limestone caves or from brines in salt lakes or from conversion of aragonite. In salt lakes it is through cation exchange process involving replacement of halite (NaCl) by CaSO₄ in the presence of calcium and SO₄-rich materials [$\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2\text{Na}^+ + \text{CaSO}_4$]. This is common in brine-rich areas under exceptionally intense evaporation of the enclosed seawater to form saline residue; and is more favourable to the formation of anhydrite. A good example is the Red Sea area where the pools lose more than 2.5m of water by evaporation per year (Friedman and Sanders, 1978). The brine-mixing hypothesis of Raup (1970) closely represents the probable source of gypsiferous materials and a good depositional model for gypsum in this Red Sea region. The conversion of aragonite (CaCO₃) occurs when sulphide ions released from decomposed constituent pyrite mineral in shale or clay react with aragonite (CaCO₃) in calcium-bearing rocks, in the presence of oxygen [released from fossil content (biota-cyanophyta)], to form gypsum (CaSO₄.2H₂O) [$\text{CaCO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{S} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CaSO}_4.2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$]. In Guyuk area, the calcium-bearing rocks (limestone) are fossiliferous, and as such very much suited for this process of gypsum formation. In carbonated areas (like the study area) gypsum is majorly formed by process of dolomitization, due to alteration by Mg-rich solutions in enclosed ancient seawater aided by numerous joints and fissures in limestone beds. In the field, many sugary textured gypsum samples were encountered on the edges of broken surfaces and within fissures in the sampled limestone. This indicates intense dolomitization. Ntekim and Zira (2001) assert that the study area has mainly magnesian limestone, thus supporting possible dolomitization of the limestone beds.

DISCUSSIONS

Integration of the field observations and physicochemical variables can contribute to our understanding of the factors that aided gypsum formation and localization in the study area.

The varying altitude and depth range of occurrence of the carrier lithologic beds within and between study locations shows that accumulation of gypsiferous materials are possible at certain altitudes and depths, but such is not restricted to particular range. Field evidence shows that some unmineralised samples occur at similar depths and in same localities with mineralized samples. This portrays that the mineralisation is more influenced by the host rock than the depth. Therefore no general rule on depth of occurrence can be applied. It is a misconception that gypsum mineralisation occurs primarily in shale and is limited to certain depth range.

Association of the studied gypsum deposits [including calcareous sandstones and limestone (dolomite?), mudstones, clays] portends a necessary lithologic association with shale for gypsum mineralisation; however, field observation shows that association with mudstone is more promising for its accumulation. Shale and limestone are each made up of diagnostic assemblage of minerals (aragonite and pyrite) and elements that would combine to form and accumulate gypsum. Actual formation of gypsum does not take place in shale materials, rather in ancient fossiliferous limestone rock units (which are aragonite-bearing) associated with shale rocks. Primary gypsum minerals form out from the decomposed carbonate material and become embedded in the consolidating fine-grained shale materials. Moreso, it is observed that mineralisation vary between locations, but specifically higher in Gunda, Lamza, Walu, Dukul, Gudenyi, Sukuliye and Lakoro areas, with large deposits of limestone (Ntekim, 1999). Even within these areas, gypsum deposit is more extensive in Gunda – Sukuliye – Lakoro axis with thicker limestone beds than the Dukul – Gudenyi – Walu axis, where gypsum accumulations occur at a greater depth range (9.02 – 13.55m). The appreciable gypsum occurrences in Dukul, Sekuliye, Gunda and Gwalura are related to the large limestone deposits in the Dukul and Sekule Formations, while the enrichment in Swenswithire and Walu areas occur relative to the abundant mudstone member of the Numanha (shale) Formation (see Fig.1).

The sparse mineralisation of the Jessu Formation is not unconnected with the low limestone content of the unit. The rock unit is limestone – rich toward the fringes bordering the overlying Sekule (in Lakoro area) and underlying Dukul Formations (in Gudenyi area). These characteristics depicts that gypsum mineralisation is related more to the chemistry of the associated/host rocks than to the altitude and/or depth of occurrence. This confirms Boyadiev's (1974) opinion that precipitation of gypsum is a function of the nature and composition of the host rock and climate, even though geomorphology, the form of landscape, orientation of the rock structure and activity of cation exchange might influence the processes of its accumulation.

It is known that dolomite content of a rock outcrop increases with depth due to continuing reaction of magnesium in solution in circulating seawater. According to Mason and Berry (1968) this increase is relative to limestone in older Formations since they have been subjected to the process of dolomitization for a longer time. In the study area, gypsum deposit is more in areas with large amounts of limestone (e.g. Gunda and Sukuliye within mid Cretaceous Sekule Formation)[see Fig.1]. Occurrences of gypsum deposits in these older limestone formations connotes that process of dolomitization is responsible for formation of the studied gypsum. The close association of the studied gypsum with highly fossiliferous-fissured magnesian limestone on stream slopes confirms dolomitization as the process of mineralisation in the area and depicts deposits probably formed in streams by the reaction of sulphides on limestone, and the water drained into inland lakes where it evaporated. According to Read (1970) this process leaves gypsum in layers of differing thickness and crystals of various sizes and shapes, as observed in the study area. Anaerobic reaction leading to the breakdown of the rich fossil contents of the limestone rock units provided the sulphide needed for gypsum formation in the area.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of the field observations gypsum mineralisation is possible at varying altitudes and depths but is not restricted to any particular depth range. The fact that mineralisation occurs at various depths closely associated with similar lithologic (limestone) units in every location depicts that gypsum mineralisation is more influenced by the composition of the host rock units than the structure and/or depth of occurrence. Field evidence of gypsum minerals associated with highly fossiliferous – fissured magnesian limestone on stream slopes depicts dolomitization as the process of gypsum formation in Guyuk area. Integration of these geological variables or control factors gives a genetic model for gypsum occurrences and can be used as guide to search for more deposits in the study area in particular and other areas with similar lithologic units in general.

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Fig. 2a i)

Fig. 2a ii)

Fig. 2a iii)

Fig. 2a iv)

Fig. 2a v)

Fig. 2a vi)

Fig. 2a vii)

Fig. 2a viii)

Fig. 2a ix)

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b i)

Fig. 2b ii)

Fig. 2b

Fig. 2c

CAPTIONS TO FIGURES

Fig. 1 Map of part of Guyuk Area showing gypsum and limestone deposits

Fig. 2a i) Section at Dukul

Fig. 2a ii) Section at Gudenyi

Fig. 2a iii) Section at Lakoro

Fig. 2a iv) Section at Sukuliye

Fig. 2a v) Section at Gunda

Fig. 2a vi) Section at Gendaure

Fig. 2a vii) Section at Lamza

Fig. 2a viii) Section at Walu

Fig. 2a ix) Section at Kola

Fig. 2a Stratigraphic sections (shale/limestone/clay alternations) at study locations

Fig. 2b i) Section at Swenswithire

Fig. 2b ii) Section at Gwalura

Fig. 2b Stratigraphic sections (shale/gypsiferous shale/mudstone alternations)

Fig. 2c Stratigraphic section (sandstone/clay alternations) at Gwana

[After Cater et al,1963; Benkhelil,1985; Enu,1980]

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Table 1: DEPTH OF OCCURRENCE OF SHALE SAMPLES

Depth (m)	Altitude (m)	Location	Status
0.02	219.32	Lakoro	gypsiferous
0.05	315.05	Walu	gypsiferous
0.05	313.85	Walu	non-gypsiferous
0.1	375.7	Walu	gypsiferous
0.15	372.9	Walu	gypsiferous
0.15	257.4	Lamza	non-gypsiferous
0.23	220.06	Lakoro	gypsiferous
0.3	225.9	Sukuliye	gypsiferous
0.4	332.2	Walu	non-gypsiferous
0.53	339.53	Walu	non-gypsiferous
0.95	231.95	Gunda	gypsiferous
1.02	215.84	Lakoro	non-gypsiferous
1.1	349.92	Walu	gypsiferous
1.2	351.9	Dukul	non-gypsiferous
1.2	279.9	Gwalura	non-gypsiferous
1.29	472.59	Gudenyi	non-gypsiferous
1.29	472.89	Gudenyi	non-gypsiferous
1.3	282.8	Gwalura	gypsiferous
1.35	244.35	Gunda	non-gypsiferous
1.4	287.9	Swenswithire	gypsiferous
1.45	357.35	Dukul	gypsiferous
1.48	210.08	Lakoro	non-gypsiferous
1.5	258.9	Swenswithire	gypsiferous
1.65	259.05	Swenswithire	gypsiferous
1.75	307.75	Swenswithire	gypsiferous
2.0	280.4	Gwalura	gypsiferous
2.02	473.32	Gudenyi	gypsiferous
2.02	473.62	Gudenyi	gypsiferous
2.13	280.83	Gwalura	gypsiferous
2.2	210.4	Lakoro	non-gypsiferous
2.5	358.4	Dukul	gypsiferous
2.5	273.3	Gwalura	gypsiferous

Table 1: DEPTH OF OCCURRENCE OF SHALE SAMPLES Contd.

3.1	254.2	Lamza	non-gypsiferous
3.27	359.17	Dukul	gypsiferous
3.5	320.8	Walu	gypsiferous
3.6	330.9	Walu	gypsiferous
3.97	359.87	Dukul	gypsiferous
4.75	332.05	Walu	gypsiferous
5.2	358.8	Dukul	non-gypsiferous
5.7	359.3	Dukul	gypsiferous
8.9	362.5	Dukul	gypsiferous
9.12	336.42	Walu	gypsiferous
10.6	364.2	Dukul	non-gypsiferous
11.8	365.4	Dukul	non-gypsiferous

Table 2 DEPTH OF OCCURRENCE OF LIMESTONE AND CLAY SAMPLES

Depth (m)	Altitude (m)	Location	Status	Sample type
0.25	224.4	Sukuliye	gypsiferous	limestone
0.3	225.6	Sukuliye	gypsiferous	limestone
0.33	471.33	Gudenyi	gypsiferous	limestone
0.4	331.9	Walu	non-gypsiferous	limestone
0.55	332.35	Walu	non-gypsiferous	limestone
0.8	315.8	Walu	gypsiferous	limestone
0.85	243.85	Gunda	non-gypsiferous	limestone
0.95	244.35	Gunda	non-gypsiferous	clay
1.08	287.83	Gendaure	gypsiferous	clay
1.1	349.92	Walu	gypsiferous	clay
1.2	210.4	Lakoro	non-gypsiferous	clay
1.3	209.9	Lakoro	non-gypsiferous	limestone
2.0	233.0	Gunda	gypsiferous	limestone
2.5	278.4	Gwana	non-gypsiferous	clay
2.55	233.55	Gunda	non-gypsiferous	limestone
2.55	356.15	Dukul	gypsiferous	limestone
3.0	254.1	Lamza	non-gypsiferous	limestone
3.6	254.5	Lamza	non-gypsiferous	clay
6.25	360.3	Dukul	gypsiferous	limestone
9.95	364.0	Dukul	gypsiferous	limestone